

CELLULAR REGENERATION BASED ON DNA MODIFICATION

[Medicina, Volume 28 - Edição 128/NOV 2023 SUMÁRIO / 28/11/2023](#)

LA REGENERACIÓN CELULAR BASADA EN LA MODIFICACIÓN DEL ADN

REGISTRO DOI:10.5281/zenodo.10213769

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ABSTRACT

Genetic engineering has played a significant role in the field of medical education, serving as a specialized application in the diagnosis, treatment, and control of pathologies. Gene therapy is one of the methods employed by genetic engineering, involving the manipulation of genes using recombinant DNA. Two types of techniques are utilized: germline – the

introduction of genetic material into spermatozoa or ova – and somatic – the introduction of genetic material into any other cells. One focus of this methodology is the correction of defective genes by introducing healthy genes into individuals with various disorders, thereby contributing to the genetic improvement of individuals.

Keywords: genetics, regeneration, modification, DNA, gene therapy.

RESUMEN

La ingeniería genética ha desempeñado un papel significativo en la ciencia de la educación médica al ser una especialidad aplicada en casos de diagnóstico, tratamiento y control de patologías. La terapia génica es uno de los métodos utilizados por la ingeniería genética, que implica la manipulación de los genes mediante el ADN recombinante. Hay dos tipos de técnicas utilizadas: la germinativa, que consiste en la introducción del material genético en los espermatozoides u ovocitos, y la somática, que implica la introducción del material genético en cualquier otra célula. Uno de los enfoques de esta metodología es la corrección de genes defectuosos mediante la introducción de genes saludables en portadores de diferentes trastornos, contribuyendo así a la mejora genética de los individuos.

Palabras clave: genética, regeneración, modificación, ADN, terapia génica.

1. CONCEPTS AND DEFINITION

Genetics and heredity, combined with molecular biology, constitute one of the outbreaks of new knowledge and technologies through which humanity is undergoing a conceptual renewal or recycling” (CONSOLARO et al., 2004). In this context, genetic engineering is characterized by a set of methodologies that enable the manipulation of the genome of living microorganisms, with the consequent alteration of the capabilities of each species, according to José Alberto Neves Candeias.

Within the universe related to genetics, some terms stand out as necessary for the understanding of this present work, such as:

Table 1 – Key Terms for Understanding the Article.

TERMO	CONCEITO
Amino acid	Small molecules invariably containing a carbon atom linked to the amine group, the hydroxyl group, and a hydrogen atom. There are 20 different types of amino acids. In a simplistic manner, it can be stated that a protein represents a sequence or chain of amino acids.
Protein	They are macromolecules consisting of numerous amino acid molecules. Invariably, the amino acid has a carbon atom linked to an amino group, a hydroxyl group, and a hydrogen atom. When a protein has only a few amino acids, it can be called a peptide: di-, tri-, or polypeptide.
DNA	“DNA or deoxyribonucleic acid: a macromolecule consisting of various nucleotides, each composed of a phosphate group, a deoxyribose sugar, and a nitrogenous base. The nitrogenous base can be Cytosine, Thymine, Adenine, or Guanine. Genetic information or memory is determined by the presence of these nitrogenous bases. The phosphate group and sugar serve purely structural functions in the molecule.”
RNA	Macromolecule consisting of various nucleotides, each formed by a phosphate group, a ribose sugar, and a nitrogenous base. The nitrogenous base can be Cytosine, Uracil, Adenine, or Guanine. Thymine is exclusive to DNA, and Uracil to RNA.
Gene	It represents a sequence of nucleotides in DNA containing complete information or a complete set of instructions

	capable of guiding the cell to synthesize something or perform a specific function ¹⁵ . This segment of DNA, a sequence of nucleotides, or a file can vary in size; in other words, genes can be small or large. A gene may regulate a part of a structure, while another gene regulates another part of the same structure. In essence, genes can participate in the same process. Genes are sequentially located in DNA, or more precisely, they constitute DNA, and together with nuclear proteins, they form chromosomes. Each pair of chromosomes contains different genes. The specific location of a gene on the DNA molecule is also referred to as the gene
TERMO	CONCEITO
	locus.

CONSOLARO *et al*, 2004 **2. HISTORICAL CONTEXT OF GENETICS**

Biotechnology, a set of techniques for organism selection, manipulation, and modification, emerges from the discovery of a compound called deoxyribonucleic acid (DNA), described as the key to the development and functioning of living beings (REIS, 2009). In 1869, biochemist Johann Friedrich Miescher revealed that proteins and lipids were the main components of cells, yet his analytical methods were simple protocols compared to the cellular protein diversity. During tests, Miescher found in the nucleus ‘a white, acidic substance rich in phosphorus,’ which he named ‘nuclein’ (MENCK, 2017).

According to Dahm (2004), Miescher confirmed that nuclein, unlike proteins, contained a large amount of phosphorus, along with elements commonly found in organic molecules, such as carbon, hydrogen, oxygen, and nitrogen. After experiments with leukocytes, the biochemist discovered the presence of nuclein in cells of other tissues, suggesting nuclei be classified based on nucleins’ presence, correlating with cell functions.

In 1910, Thomas Hunt Morgan demonstrated that chromosomes carry genes, inspiring the search for the chemical identification of the gene. The chemical arrangement of nucleic acids, formerly called nucleins, was later identified by the American Phoebus Aaron Levene, proposing a tetranucleotide structure for DNA (MENK, 2017). According to Moreira (2013), in 1928, Frederick Griffith observed that live virulent bacteria could transmit their virulence to non-pathogenic live bacteria. This information transmission became known as the 'transforming principle,' later explained in experiments describing DNA as the element responsible for genetic information transmission.

Figure 1 – Photograph of DNA molecules taken in 1950.

Source: Available at <https://www.quantumuniverse.nl/rosalind-franklin-en-haar-foto-vandna>.

Accessed on: October 26, 2023.

Francis Crick and James D. Watson concluded in 1951 that the DNA molecule is helical, and they also suggested that, in addition to the semi-conservative nature of DNA molecule duplication, 'the transcription of the RNA molecule could be obtained by simple complementarity of one of the DNA strands' (MENCK, 2017). In 1972, Paul Berg demonstrated the technology of recombinant DNA, based on a protocol for manipulating DNA from cells to produce specific proteins. Consequently, this technique allowed the creation of new gene combinations, often nonexistent in

nature, through the location, isolation, alteration, and transplantation of DNA segments from one species to another (JACKSON, 1972).

In this context, it is evident that the expansion of knowledge about the human genome, coupled with advances in applied technology, enabled the direct manipulation of DNA through its recombination, according to the needs of the scientific community. Therefore, biotechnology and, consequently, genetic engineering began to be used as significant tools for genetic improvement (REIS, 2009).

3. EVOLUTION OF RESEARCH RELATED TO CROSSING AND GENE THERAPY

Gene therapy, through the development of techniques and subsequent protocols, has enabled the manipulation of an individual's genetic makeup, despite encountering numerous challenges in certain procedures. From this perspective, this science holds the position of a "modern salvation" in addressing health-related issues, such as the cure of genetically inherited diseases or even conditions acquired during life, such as cancer, heart diseases, and viral infections (MENK, 2007).

Watson and Crick (1970) defined gene therapy as the ability to achieve genetic improvement by correcting altered (mutated) genes and/or specific codifications with the primary objective of therapeutic treatment. This procedure became feasible due to advances in genetic science and bioengineering, allowing the manipulation of vectors for the delivery of extrachromosomal material into target cells.

A lot of people claim to be concerned about the change in our genetic instructions. But these [genetic instructions] are merely a product of evolution, shaped to adapt us to certain conditions that may no longer exist. We all know how imperfect we are. Why not become a little more fit for survival?" (WATSON AND CRICK, 1970).

One of the most utilized techniques involves the application of recombinant DNA, where the gene of interest and/or a healthy gene is inserted into a vector, which can be plasmid, nanostructured, or viral. The latter is predominantly chosen for its efficiency in invading cells and introducing its genetic material. Despite various successful protocols, the gene therapy process remains complex, requiring ongoing developments (GONÇALVES, 2017).

Gonçalves (2017) further states that specific cells requiring treatment must be identified and arranged accessibly. From this perspective, an effective means of distributing gene copies to cells must be available, and both diseases and their close genetic connections need complete comprehension.

There is also a question regarding the target cell type in gene therapy, currently divided into two major groups: germline gene therapy and somatic cell gene therapy. In germline gene therapy, germ cells, such as sperm and egg cells, are modified by introducing functional genes that integrate into the genome. Changes are hereditary and pass on to subsequent generations. In theory, this approach should be highly effective in combating genetic and hereditary diseases (GONÇALVES, 2017).

According to the aforementioned author, somatic cell gene therapy involves transferring therapeutic genes to somatic cells of a patient. Any modification and effects are confined solely to the patient and are not inherited by future generations.

Additionally, there is the prevalence of a process known as RNA interference. In summary, this process involves a cellular mechanism responsible for post-transcriptional gene silencing (PTGS) acting on messenger RNA (mRNA). It relies on a double-stranded RNA (dsRNA) molecule that, when incorporated in its active form into an

intracytoplasmic complex, binds to a complementary nucleotide sequence located on the target mRNA, thereby causing silencing through inhibition of translation and/or mRNA degradation (FRANÇA et al, 2010).

França et al (2010) asserts that there is evidence that dsRNAs are also involved in maintaining the condensation of chromatin regions and suppressing transcription in the vicinity of these regions. However, the association between transcriptional gene silencing (TGS) and RNAi is not yet fully clarified.

4. GENE THERAPY IN HEMOPHILIA B

Gene therapy has shown great success in some coagulopathies, notably hemophilia B, a recessive X-linked inherited disorder resulting from a deficiency in factor IX production in the liver, disrupting the coagulation mechanism. Symptoms typically include severe bleeding from minor injuries and even spontaneous hemorrhages. Additionally, there may be hematoma formation in muscles or joints, intracranial hemorrhage, or bleeding in vital organs (FLORES et al., 2004).

Flores et al. (2004) note that the initial diagnosis is made through blood coagulation tests, Activated Partial Thromboplastin Time (APTT), Coagulation Time (CT), Prothrombin Time (PT), Thrombin Time (TT), and Bleeding Time (BT). Once the diagnosis is confirmed, the treatment involves the application of a concentrated factor IX. Since coagulation factors are sourced from blood, there is a risk of contamination by agents such as HIV and hepatitis.

In cases like these, gene therapy proves to be of great utility, not only preventing the transmission of infectious agents but also yielding extremely positive results. In recent research led by Kay and colleagues in 1993, a virus, adeno-associated with gene 5 responsible for factor IX expression, was injected directly into the hepatic artery of severe hemophilia B patients. The vector caused no side effects, and the transgene expression achieved high therapeutic levels for eight weeks. It

is also correct to state that in vivo therapy attains satisfactory levels of factor IX, even though the transgene may not express for an extended period (FARAH, 2007).”

5. CURRENT STATE OF HUMAN DNA MODIFICATION AND REGENERATION

The topic of ‘Human DNA Modification’ gained unprecedented attention in 2020 when scientists Emmanuelle Charpentier and Jennifer Doudna were awarded the 2020 Nobel Prize in Chemistry for their discovery of the groundbreaking genetic technology known as CRISPR/Cas9. This revolutionary gene-editing tool is contributing to new therapies for cancer and pioneering studies aimed at curing hereditary diseases.

The innovative features of the CRISPR/Cas9 system, particularly its ability to identify the system through base-pairing interactions between guide RNA and its target DNA, have positioned it ahead of other genetic therapy technologies (HEIDARI, 2015).

As stated by the aforementioned author, the meta-specificity of CRISPR/Cas9, coupled with its ease of use and effectiveness, has enabled its diverse applications in research, medicine, and biotechnology. Primarily designed as a genome-editing tool, CRISPR/Cas9 has been widely employed since 2013 across various cell lines and organisms, including mice, rats, fruit flies, nematodes, frogs, monkeys, as well as plants such as rice, wheat, soybeans, and tobacco. It has also been applied to fungi, organoids, embryonic stem cells, and induced pluripotent stem cells.

The CRISPR/Cas9 gene-editing tool functions as an associated protein, known as Cas. In summary, this CrisprCas9 technology allows direct targeting of defective genes as a guiding tool to reach specific target cells. In this process, the Cas9 enzyme (a type of nuclease) cuts both strands of

double-stranded DNA, creating space for the insertion of new stretch sequences. This novel technology has transformed once-impossible genetic procedures into straightforward 'cut and paste' operations. It is essential to note that the primary purpose of utilizing this technology is to cure genetic diseases in the germline, affecting not only the patient but also their offspring and all subsequent generations. Although currently illegal, this technology paves the way for numerous new studies and opportunities in the field of genetic science (SGANZERLA, 2020).

According to Helinski (2013), in a genetic crossing study, the luciferase gene from the firefly *Photinus pyralis* was employed to produce light in plant cells and transgenic plants. In this process, a portion of the luciferase gene's DNA was introduced into protoplast cells of plants (*Daucus carota*) through electroporation. As a result, the plants were able to produce light, and the luminescence pattern, though detected in most plant organs (leaves, stems, roots), seemed to reflect a specific organ distribution."

Figure 2 – Photograph of a genetically modified leaf with the luciferase gene.

Source: Available at <https://www.sciencemag.org/>.

Accessed on: October 31, 2023.

The luciferase gene has been a crucial tool for studying gene expression in plant and animal cells. In genetic engineering, the luciferase gene proves to be uniquely valuable as a marker, paving the way for other procedures involving DNA modifications along with Genetic Crossing.

With the tremendous and rapid advancement in genetic engineering, human limb regeneration has garnered attention in the field of genetic science through cross breeding between species. Scientists conducted in-depth research on the axolotl, a salamander with remarkable regenerative capabilities. In 2018, its genome, ten times larger than the human genome, became the longest genome to be sequenced. However, understanding the function of genes involved in axolotl regeneration poses a challenge because these genes are contained in numerous repeated lengths of DNA.

Flores (2020) reports that researchers at Yale University have developed a new screening platform to bring the possibility of applying this regeneration process in humans closer. Increasingly, genetic technologies and resources have allowed researchers to explore the molecular origins of regenerative capacity in certain salamander species, such as axolotls, capable of fully regenerating limbs. Through various combinations, embryos, and general techniques, including CRISPR/Cas9 mutagenesis, genetic function, and the fidelity of limb regeneration can be explored. This enables the study of specific gene regeneration functions that may be necessary for other essential processes, such as organogenesis, morphological tissue changes, and other fundamental embryonic processes.

6. MATERIALS AND METHODS

In the development of this research, the following methodological steps were established: formulation of the guiding question, selection and acquisition of articles or books, evaluation of pre-selected studies, discussion of the obtained results, and the presentation of the integrative review.

The first step originated from the following guiding question: In what aspects can DNA modification promote the regeneration of cells, tissues, and limbs in humans?

The second step consisted of the selection of articles and books through searches in scientific literature, covering the period from July 1970 to April 2021, in the following databases: Virtual Health Library, Virtual Library of the University Center of Espírito Santo (UNESC), DataSUS, PubMed, and Springer.

The inclusion criteria established for the selection of scientific articles were: original articles that addressed the guiding question, with electronic availability in full text and published between 1970 and 2021, in Portuguese and/or English languages, and also containing, in their titles and/or abstracts, the following Health Science Descriptors (DeCS): 'genetic therapy,' 'genetic therapy,' 'somatic gene therapy,' and 'gene therapy.'

Articles that did not meet the mentioned inclusion criteria were excluded.

7. INTEGRATIVE REVIEW AND DISCUSSION OF RESULTS

For the development of the theoretical framework of the study, 12 articles were used, following the selection criteria presented in the previous section. Among these articles, 6 were chosen to compose the integrative review and are presented in Table

2."

Table 2 – Results and Conclusions of Selected Articles.

Authors/year	Article Title	Results	Conclusions
Geraldo, J. M., & Montañó Valencia, C. J. 2023.	Use of Nanostructured Systems in Cancer Treatment	Nanomedicine, a convergent domain of nanotechnology and medicine,	Among the various lines of action that have been explored, genetic

		offers a variety of benefits	manipulation also emerges as a
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			compared to the traditional therapeutic approach to cancer, such as increased sensitivity to radiation, versatility, effectiveness in drug administration, and regulated release of chemotherapeutic agents.	promising suggest support treatment potential associated with nanostructure systems provide synergistic effect. They could provide the inhibition of metastasis markers increasing expectations for patients more advanced stages.
Sousa, et al. 2023.	Osteogenic mesenchymal cells bone protein 9	potential of stem overexpressing morphogenetic	Based on the literature analyzed, it is feasible to conclude that the amplification of CTM and BMP-9 enables the	The application of tools enabling genomic analysis enhance adaptability the asse

			<p>restoration of bone tissue in both in vivo and in vitro research. The procedure highlights the renewal process in extensive existing bone defects, being recognized as a promising and beneficial therapy in contrast to transplants.</p>	<p>context, providing expanded opportunities for bone formation in the field of health science compared to other regenerative approaches such as currently existing autologous transplants.</p>
<p>SOUZA, et al. 2015.</p>	<p>Regulation and Activation of Satellite Cells During Muscle Regeneration</p>		<p>In the presence of muscle injury, quiescent satellite cells are activated by various growth and proliferation factors. Proliferation is positively influenced by HGF, IGF,</p>	<p>The MGF myogenin and MRF4 stimulate differentiation of myoblasts into myotubes. Among other factors that regulate the proliferative cycle of</p>

		<p>androgens, IInsulin. differentiation satellite cells myoblasts stimulated myogenic MyoD, Myf5, VEGF.</p>	<p>, and The of into is by factors and</p>	<p>SCs are non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs and glucocorticoids, myostatin, and T3.</p>
<p>Furtado, R. N. 2019.</p>	<p>Genetic Editing: Risks and Benefits of Human DNA Modification</p>	<p>Genetic modification techniques have been developed since the 1990s, representing, for some authors, a true revolution in the field of biotechnology⁴. The procedure is called this way because it is capable of 'removing' specific segments of DNA and introducing new genes in place—both germline and somatic cells can be modified². In the case of germline cells (eggs and sperm cells) and precursor cells, genetic alterations are passed on to descendants. Some researchers also include embryos in the early stage of formation under this designation. On the other</p>		<p>The editing occurs in two steps: first, identification and cutting of the DNA, then, repair of the molecule. Four techniques are used: 1) meganucleases; 2) zinc-finger nucleases; 3) transcription activator-like effector nucleases; and 4) CRISPR-Cas9. These tools have recognition devices to adhere to specific sequences of the target DNA and cleavage devices to cut the</p>

		hand, somatic cells refer to all other	nucleotides. After the cut, double-strand breaks occur, triggering cellular repair mechanisms, such as NHEJ to silence genes and HDR to regenerate double-strand breaks using external DNA templates.
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		cells in the organism, but their changes are not hereditary.	
Oliveira, C. S., Nascimento, M., de Almeida Junior, E., Crusoé, M., Bahia, P., & Rosa, F. P. 2010.	Advances and Applications of Tissue Bioengineering	Currently, there are still many controversies regarding the ethical, political, and social issues related to the use of stem cells for therapeutic applications. Despite this, several investigations have already been	The combination of gene therapy, tissue engineering, and biomaterials has the potential to create synthetic environments that provide the necessary stimuli to promote the

		<p>conducted with various types of existing stem cells, as discussed. However, more comprehensive molecular-level studies are essential to precisely understand the factors influencing stem cell differentiation.</p>	<p>formation of functional tissues. Significant progress has been made in utilizing structures that facilitate the delivery of cells, genes, and proteins to injuries. For new biomaterials to be successfully employed in tissue engineering, there is an essential need to investigate the interactions between cells and these materials.</p>
<p>Martins, R. S., Siqueira, M. G., Silva, C. F., Plese, J. P. P. 2005.</p>	<p>Basic Mechanisms of Nerve Regeneration</p>	<p>If axon reconstruction does not occur, changes may arise in the target organs. Muscle fibers atrophy, assuming a more</p>	<p>It is noted that the renewal is an intricate mechanism whose effectiveness depends on the occurrence and</p>

		<p>rounded shape from the originally peripheral to central part of the cell. Some of these changes can</p>	<p>integration of various phases subject to numerous cellular and molecular signals. Thus, it is easy to understand that</p>
		<p>be observed a few weeks after the injury. Neuromuscular junctions also shrink and disappear, a process that begins three months after axonal injury. Muscle tissue is replaced by fibrotic tissue between 12 and 24 months after nerve injury.</p>	<p>although the renewal process is highly effective when observed in its entirety, the absence of a step results in the detriment of the entire process, leading to unsatisfactory clinical consequences. The challenge for the coming decades is to translate, for clinical application, all the advances achieved from understanding</p>

			renewal, enhancing success rates after surgical treatment of traumatic nerve injuries.
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8. CONCLUSION

Understanding and manipulating the genetic code have paved revolutionary paths in science and medicine. The fundamental molecule, DNA, serves as the cornerstone of genetic information, with the nucleotide sequence determining cellular characteristics and functions. The historical evolution, from Miescher's discoveries to Watson and Crick's revelation of DNA's helical structure, has shaped our understanding of heredity. Biotechnology has emerged from this knowledge, and gene therapy has become a 'modern salvation' for various genetic and acquired conditions. The DNA recombinant technique, introduced by Paul Berg, has enabled unprecedented genetic manipulations, creating new gene combinations and, consequently, advancing therapeutic possibilities. Hemophilia B exemplifies the success of gene therapy, where introducing the factor IX gene through viral vectors has yielded positive results, avoiding risks associated with conventional therapy. Moreover, the CRISPR/Cas9 technology has revolutionized genetic editing, providing a precise and efficient tool for correcting defective genes. The ability to modify human DNA, exemplified by the 2020 Nobel Prize in Chemistry, marks a milestone in genetic science.

The CRISPR/Cas9 genetic scissors, with their target specificity, have opened new experimental opportunities, allowing precise gene editing in various species. Human DNA regeneration and modification, notably the regenerative capacity of the axolotl, point toward a promising future. Genetic research, coupled with genetic crossing and CRISPR/Cas9

technology, provides insights into human limb regeneration.

Understanding the genes involved in axolotl regeneration propels research into specific functions, opening doors to innovative therapeutic applications. In summary, the modification of human DNA is a fascinating and promising journey with profound implications for medicine and our understanding of life.

As we push the boundaries of genetic engineering, new therapeutic possibilities and scientific advancements emerge, pointing toward a future where genetic manipulation may become a common tool in the pursuit of health and disease cure.

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Arq Bras Neurocir 24(1)

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ISSN: 1678-0817

CNPJ:

48.728.404/0001-
22

CAPES –

Coordenação de Aperfeiçoamento de Pessoal de Nível Superior (CAPES), fundação do Ministério da Educação (MEC), desempenha papel fundamental na expansão e consolidação da pós-graduação stricto sensu (mestrado e doutorado) em todos os estados da Federação.

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